

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-224-AD-H 30% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	55	Acq. Method Set:	30%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 278
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	282.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 282.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/31/2023 7:28:19 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/4/2023 7:38:31 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.890	1130709	34.63	110150
2	6.446	1080710	33.10	94661
3	11.902	537076	16.45	22467
4	12.995	516358	15.82	19454

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-236-AD-30% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221201
Vial:	93	Acq. Method Set:	30%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 134
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	282.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 282.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/1/2022 4:41:58 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/4/2023 7:34:57 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.758	16032	0.52	2115
2	6.600	3011550	96.96	255238
3	12.139	13362	0.43	562
4	13.170	65120	2.10	2397